

D5.3.Polarisation Report

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This document is available for download at <https://dradproject.com>

About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalization and polarization in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and wider social contexts driving radicalization, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualizes this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarization) with the goal of moving towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalization programmes. We intend to identify the building blocks of radicalization, which include a sense of being victimized; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures; and coming under the influence of "us vs them" identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Iraq, Jordan, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs, and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion, and de-radicalization.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation-states adapt to new security challenges. The process of mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts will be crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that processes of radicalization often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national frameworks of justice. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analyzing, and devising solutions to online radicalization will be central to the project's aims.

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Introduction

The rise of the far-right on a global scale has recently legitimised its politics whilst strengthening systemic racism (Mondon and Winter 2020), as well as social exclusion. Moreno-Almeida and Gerbaudo (2021, 885) recently identified renewed stream of far-right discourses as racist and anti-immigrant, anti-semitic and Islamophobic, anti-feminist and anti-LGBTQIA+, anti-leftist, anti-establishment and reactionary and ethno-and ultranationalist. In the last few years, burgeoning literature studying a rather unleashed far-right online extremism, has examined how far-right publics make their audiences thanks to what social media platforms avail to them (see Munn 2019; Baele et al. 2020; Holt et al. 2020; Wahlström et al. 2021). This is namely a rampant circulation of their narratives without fact-checking and perennial othering in an unscrupulous manner. Within the existing studies of the political communication of far-right groups and/or ordinary far-right users, the visual side of political mobilisation has been neglected until recently (see Doerr 2017). Visual symbols, posters and videos are crucial forms of the representation of far-right political mobilisation today as they provide rich materials for content creators to reach their onlookers – even if ghoulish at times – and make new audiences by exploiting accessible, ubiquitous, and immediate features of visual communication (Doerr et al. 2015). Following Aiello and Parry (2019), our aim in this report is to represent the ways renewed far-right ideas and identities are casted, shaped and maintained through visuals that enable performing the self, communicating a collective identity and/or foregrounding the difference of “others” (e.g., refugees, Muslims etc.). This ultimately serves to construct a divided society. The visual repository presented in this report rests on D.Rad 5.2 country reports. As such, the report will first introduce the theoretical and empirical context of 5.3, followed by brief summaries of D.Rad 5.2 country reports.

This report is a visual repository exploring and presenting the polarisation potential of mundane events. Hence, it showcases how far-right users exploit visual techniques and how such techniques facilitate their exploitation to perform overtly racist and white supremacist social and political identities, particularly in the aftermath of Europe’s so-called refugee crisis era. It examines promotional and propagandist visual media objects, produced and/or circulated within the interconnected far-right, alt-right, white supremacist, anti-immigrant, anti-black and Islamophobic socio-cultural-political networks in this period. The depiction of the outgroup in these images strengthens already existing divisions in the country contexts covered in the EU Horizon 2020 funded D.Rad De-radicalisation in Europe and Beyond: Detect, Resolve, Reintegrate project.

As an extension of the rampant racist public sphere following the so-called refugee crisis, the WP5 has aimed to understand how subcultural visual media contents have reached out to more mainstream audiences using image-based media platforms and to delineate discourse worlds and organisation patterns of do-it-yourself media, reflecting on the far-right’s claims of injustice, grievance, and alienation, which ultimately leads to wider polarisation. As such, we aim to understand the ways subcultural image-based content transpire from echo-chambers and reach more mainstream audiences through features and affordances inherent to social media platforms and visual media. The repository of images of far-right visual communication

includes but it is not limited to delineating the dominant visual practices and strategies, production dynamics, discourses, distribution, and/or organisation patterns of visual media, produced by both professional and relatively amateur groups and individuals that have radicalised around their perception of immigration, refugees, and ethnic and racial minorities.

While research is limited, some patterns emerge when examining images in the context of online misogyny, homophobia, and transphobia. Memes are central, using humour as both a vehicle for radicalisation and resistance. Concerning misogyny, online rhetoric seeks to objectify, sexualise, and dehumanise women and bolster hegemonic masculinity. With transphobic and homophobic content, gay and trans people are presented as societal others, working to reinforce heteronormative views of gender and sexuality. Conversely, feminist and pro-trans content uses memes to mock sexist and transphobic beliefs. Women have also been observed using visual social media to reclaim their bodies and create spaces for resistance, and the visibility of gay and trans bodies is similarly an important means of empowerment. The report also showcases images produced by users that aim to challenge and resist the polarisation and dehumanisation created by far-right visual publics.

In order to give a background to these images, below, we are also summarising below the country reports that have already examined them.

The D.Rad Austria 5.2 report focuses on right-wing extremism, analysing (radicalised) narratives that revolve around misogyny, homophobia, sexism and transphobia in the media, production, and circulation of media objects by prominent stakeholders of radicalisation, and the attempts to counter these narratives by stakeholders of de-radicalisation and by citizens in the context of communication. The report identifies that gendered radicalisation traits online are a continuation of offline battles that are not confined to online spheres. As such, online activities create opportunities towards political confrontation, as well as new forms of engagement with like-minded others, rather than creating platforms of dialogue between stakeholders of radicalisation and stakeholders of de-radicalisation in Austria.

The DRad Finland 5.2 country report examines the relationship between mediated hegemonic gender representations, violence, and extremism by analysing empirical evidence collected from social media through the lens of I-GAP (Injustice-Grievance-Alienation-Polarisation). The data consists of posts by three actors that are identified in this study as agents of radicalisation, three de-radicalisation actors, and three ordinary citizens who are addressing these topics publicly. With the agents of radicalisation, the report aims to illustrate how extreme narratives revolving around misogyny, homophobia, sexism, and transphobia are expressed online using visual and communicative tools, how they disseminate their messages and how their audiences respond to them. The report also analyses how these hegemonic gender representations are countered by the de-radicalisation actors and ordinary citizens and the ways they aim to tackle alienation, othering, polarization, and grievance.

The DRad France 5.2 country report looks at the online activity of two prominent far-right political figures, Marine Le Pen and Eric Zemmour, and a far-right online activist, Papacito, to understand violent and extremist narratives in the context of gender. The report identified an intrinsic link between far-right and misogynistic ideology, showing a distinct overlap between the two among the French far-right. This is followed by an investigation of how both organisations, such as the French government and feminist/LGBTQ+ NGOs, and ordinary citizens use their online presence to undermine misogyny. Strategies include identifying when far-right discourse is misleading and manipulative, organising public events and awareness campaigns, and using hashtags to spread feminist messages, such as #LesPrincessesOntDesPoils (#PrincessesHaveBodyHair).

The DRad Germany 5.2 country report investigates the discursive lines present in far-right rhetoric on gender in Germany, with an analysis of memes, infographics and TikTok. The findings of the report show that, first, the right-wing promotes hegemonic gender roles, particularly hegemonic masculinity, as necessary to preserve the “normality” of society and to solve Germany’s demographic crisis, also implicitly promoting right-wing spaces and political struggles as ways for men to reinvigorate their masculinity and confidence. Second, the right-wing positions itself against gender mainstreaming, commonly referred to as ‘gender hysteria’ or ‘gender Gaga’. Finally, we find that right-wing actors instrumentalise individual women and members of the LGBT+ community in their spaces to legitimize their discourse, showcasing them as tokens portrayed as honest, ‘normal’ people distinguished from the overly progressive nature of mainstream LGBT+ and feminist rhetoric. The report also analyses how progressive stakeholders of deradicalisation and ordinary users engage with the topic. The report highlights that the former’s style of communication has limited potential to speak persuasively to the far-right, a problem exacerbated by algorithms. This is also the case with the latter, although viral content created by ordinary users showed to spark more debate in the comment sections.

The DRad Hungary 5.2 report looks at toxic masculinity, gender discrimination, sexism, and anti-LGBTQ+ ideology in the context of politically induced polarization and the political elite under the Fidesz government. This centres on neo-Turanism, a right-wing ideology that rests upon mythical interpretations of Hungarian prowess and valour as fighters and state builders, which inevitably indicate masculine superiority. Thus, radicalisation in the context of Hungary is particularly mainstream, led by the government and prominent political figures. The report then looks at deradicalisation efforts and methods of countering such narratives, for example, from female politicians and feminist NGOs who use their social media presence to criticise anti-feminist and anti-LGBTQ+ laws in Hungary. There are also examples of ordinary citizens similarly using their platforms to promote feminist and LGBTQ+ causes.

The DRad Italy 5.2 report studies radicalizing collective agents engaging in anti-gendered communication targeting women and LGBTQIA+ persons, and de-radicalizing collectives offering counter-narratives, and at citizen communication also exerting a de-radicalizing power through a critical discourse analysis of posts made on social media platforms. The report shows that the developments of mediated hegemonic gender representation stem from private TV becoming popular in the years of the Berlusconi government and the ways these topics have also made their way into the new social media. The findings delineate, first, that a misogynist portrayal of women as silent ornaments, which leads to increasingly vicious attacks on women who go against this stereotype and speak their minds, in particular female politicians. Second, Catholicism is very strong and very politicised in Italy, with the Vatican even increasing its influence on national politics over the last years.

The DRad Kosovo 5.2 country report investigates media objects developed by both actors that promote radical narratives and those that seek to counter them in Kosovo. It assesses the pathways that have influenced hegemonic gender representations in Kosovo by engaging with the historical relevance of the 1999 war and its effects on gender presentation. In doing so, the report seeks to develop insights into how social media platforms are used in driving both radical and de-radical narratives and the ways in which audiences engage and respond to them. This report is based on the premise that there is a need to systematically examine how misogynistic narratives are circulated online in Kosovo, and how actors reflect upon them based on their online performances.

The DRad Serbia 5.2 country report focuses on male agency and power in both traditional and online media, with the examined actors ranging from members of the political elite to YouTube personalities, to ordinary individuals to understand narratives around male violence, toxic masculinity, and misogyny. In particular, the report looks at narratives around infamous rape and sexual harassment cases, some of which worked to promulgate and normalise sexism.

The report then explores responses to these examples of male violence and misogyny, as well as efforts to counter these narratives. Examples include online campaigns and protests from women's grassroots organisations and left-wing online news outlets, as well as efforts from feminist citizen actors who used their social media presence to fight against misogyny.

The DRad Slovenia 5.2 country report investigates anti-gender and pro-gender actors and discourses in Slovenia, in particular the opposition to the so-called *gender ideology* and celebrations of gender diversity. Using Gramscian concepts of hegemony and counter-hegemony, the report employs a discursive analysis of governmental and non-governmental actors, including anti- and pro-LGBTQ+ NGOs, far-right groups, and grassroots activist collectives. Since gender ideology is considered a (cultural) Marxist invention in Slovenia, the report focuses on the agents of radicalisation that propel this hegemonic conspiratorial discourse. However, to examine the power of counter-narratives, the report also analyses media presence and discourses of various non-heteronormative activist NGOs and initiatives, as well as ordinary citizen collectives engaging in innovative discursive criticism.

The DRad Turkey 5.2 country report uncovers media representation and presentation of anti-gender discourse as well as the collective and ordinary displays against gendered radicalization. First, it shows that discrimination and attacks against non-heteronormative individuals and organizations are neither sporadic nor isolated in Turkey. On the contrary, discrimination becomes organized and mobilized. The report shows the ways in which the expansion of anti-gender discourse is related to the overall closing of the political space and the rise of authoritarian populism. Second, the report delineates that there is an increasing awareness among the citizens and diverse oppositional groups that anti-gender discourse is related to the authoritarian turn and state-led radicalization. The report elaborates on this argument by giving examples from collective agents against anti-gender radicalization and non-LGBTQI+ organizations' increasing recognition that their agendas are not mutually exclusive.

The DRad UK 5.2 country report studies the online agents of far-right extremism and the ways in which citizens and members of civil society tackle social and political problems related to radicalisation in the UK. By looking at the patterns of visual political communication on social media platforms, the report showcases everyday expressions of sexism, misogyny, transphobia, and racialisation in the UK. The report identifies several reasons to explain the underlying issues that help the formation of performative masculinity and its mainstreaming as a far-right reference point for wider users and audiences. First, the Brexit vote in 2016 and subsequent right-wing, nativistic, and populist political leaders such as former Prime Minister Boris Johnson, have made certain radicalised and divisive narratives mainstream in the UK. Second, the algorithmic systems underlying new technologies bolster already existing social inequalities and exclusions as well as the communicative tools of social media platforms and apps that boost the visibility of various forms of online hate. Although the report is interested in users' engagement with newer platforms (e.g. TikTok) and the ways these actors and stakeholders engage with them, the report also analyses different types of radicalisation and deradicalisation on legacy social media platforms (e.g. YouTube) where narratives hit the mainstream, are legitimised in society, and reach wider audiences and receive wider support.

In conclusion, WP5 presents a review of visual media, radicalisation and polarisation in a wide range of European countries from the centre to the periphery, from democratic to authoritarian. Today, global social media platforms increasingly take proactive measures to crack down on accounts promoting extremist views, especially text-based legacy platforms such as X/Twitter (Mahl et. al. 2021). Considering content moderation and exploitation, immediacy, and ephemerality particularly related to visual content informed by extremist opinions, ideas and ideologies, this report also serves as an archival practice of Internet visual cultures (Crawford et al. 2021). This report builds a visual repository to present various exemplars of how

mundane and everyday imagery, if showcased by the extreme right, can have a polarising potential.

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Austria

1. Collective agents of radicalisation

1.1 Burschenschaft Teutonia

Snapshot taken from the website <http://www.teutonia.at/> [no date, retrieved 2022/02/22]

Snapshot taken from Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/TeutoniaWien/>.

[published 2022/01/15, retrieved 2022/02/22].

Translation picture: political discussion culture. I am a tolerant, educated, open-minded leftist. And if you do not submit immediately to my opinion, then you are a racist, misogynist, anti-gay, anti-Islam, die-hard, violent, fascist, right-wing extremist, inciting Nazi-ass.

Translation caption: Frustration, because 50 types of gender have been invented but none of them fits.

1.2 Ring Freiheitlicher Jugend

Snapshot taken from Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/FJOesterreich>

[published 2021/08/31, retrieved 2022/02/22].

Translation picture: Sharia-compliant: Thermal spa Vöslau organises bathing day for women only.

Translation caption: At the Vöslau thermal baths, there will be a bathing day just for women in September. “Especially in summer, many places, especially outdoor pools, are places that are not safe for many female-read people”, explains Madeleine Alizadeh, an Iranian-born Viennese “influencer”, who organizes the bathing day. “Beauty standards, body standards and ‘male gaze’ are not allowed to enter”. Entry fees will be donated to an Afghan women’s club. Alizadeh had assisted migrants on their way to Austria during the 2015 asylum crisis.

1.3 Martin Sellner

"Globohomo", Transhumanismus & der Regenbogenterror | COMPACT REZENSION
08/21

Snapshot taken from Odysee <https://odysee.com/@MartinSellner:d/compact0821:3>
[published 2021/08/03, retrieved 2022/02/22]

Translation title: "Globohomo", transhumanism and the rainbow-terror | COMPACT review
08/21

2. Collective agents of de-radicalisation

2.1 Österreichische Hochschüler_innenschaft der Universität Wien

All snapshots taken from Instagram https://www.instagram.com/oeh_uniwien/

[published 2022/01/21, retrieved 2022/02/22]

Translation picture: No place for Nazis at the university. ÖH Uni Vienna.

Translation caption: We also support the anti-fascist demonstration on Thursday, 27.01 at 18.30 o'clock at the university ramp!

(The rest of the text in the caption is a copy of the text on the pictures)

Translation picture: As an ideological training ground for new cadres, *Burschenschaften* (fraternities) are the backbone of Austrian right-wing extremism. From their ranks stem FPÖ politicians as well as leading heads of the Identitarians or convicted neo-Nazis.

The image shows a red poster on the left and a screenshot of an Instagram post on the right. The poster features a white logo at the top left, a white circle with a red '7' inside, and the text: "Burschenschaften sind eine elitäre Seilschaft die in alter Männerbund-Manier ihren rechten Kameraden Einfluss & Jobs verschaffen." At the bottom right of the poster is the "OH UNI WIEN" logo. The Instagram post is from the account "oeh_uniwien" and is dated "21. JANUAR". The post text reads: "oeh_uniwien Auch wir rufen zur antifaschistischen Demonstration am Donnerstag, den 27.01 um 18.30 Uhr bei der Uni Rampe auf! Als ideologische Kaderschmiede sind Burschenschaften das Rückgrat des österreichischen Rechtsextremismus. Aus ihren Reihen stammen FPÖ-Politiker ebenso wie führende Köpfe der Identitären oder verurteilte Neonazis. Burschenschaften sind eine elitäre Seilschaft die in alter Männerbund-Manier ihren rechten Kameraden Einfluss & Jobs verschaffen. An den Universitäten wollen sie durch ihr auftreten in Couleur Mitglieder werben und Andersdenkende einschüchtern. Es gilt, das völkische Treiben der ewiggestrigen Burschenschafter an der Uni und ihre gesellschaftliche Normalisierung zu beenden." The post has 131 likes and a comment section.

Translation picture: *Burschenschaften* are an elitist clique that, in the old male fraternity manner, provide their right-wing comrades with influence and jobs.

The image shows a red poster on the left and a screenshot of an Instagram post on the right. The poster features a white logo at the top left, a white circle with a red '7' inside, and the text: "An den Universitäten wollen sie durch ihr Auftreten in Couleur Mitglieder werben und Andersdenkende einschüchtern. Es gilt, das völkische Treiben der ewiggestrigen Burschenschafter an der Uni und ihre gesellschaftliche Normalisierung zu beenden." At the bottom right of the poster is the "OH UNI WIEN" logo. The Instagram post is from the account "oeh_uniwien" and is dated "21. JANUAR". The post text reads: "oeh_uniwien Auch wir rufen zur antifaschistischen Demonstration am Donnerstag, den 27.01 um 18.30 Uhr bei der Uni Rampe auf! Als ideologische Kaderschmiede sind Burschenschaften das Rückgrat des österreichischen Rechtsextremismus. Aus ihren Reihen stammen FPÖ-Politiker ebenso wie führende Köpfe der Identitären oder verurteilte Neonazis. Burschenschaften sind eine elitäre Seilschaft die in alter Männerbund-Manier ihren rechten Kameraden Einfluss & Jobs verschaffen. An den Universitäten wollen sie durch ihr auftreten in Couleur Mitglieder werben und Andersdenkende einschüchtern. Es gilt, das völkische Treiben der ewiggestrigen Burschenschafter an der Uni und ihre gesellschaftliche Normalisierung zu beenden." The post has 131 likes and a comment section.

Translation picture: At universities, they want to recruit members and intimidate dissenters by appearing in couleur. It is necessary to put an end to the *völkisch* activities of the diehard fraternity members at the university and to their social normalization.

2.2 Frauenvolksbegehren

All snapshots taken from Instagram <https://www.instagram.com/frauenvolksbegehren/> [published 2020/11/27, retrieved 2022/02/22]

Translation picture: Just like a miniskirt is not an incitement to harassment, neither is a headscarf.

Translation caption: Asma Aiad is an activist, youth worker, and artist. Among other things, @asmaaiad deals with the topics of construction and deconstruction of racisms. She is also a spokesperson* for the Black Voices Anti-Racism Petition that can already be signed. More info at: @blackvoicesvolksbegehren

We are using #16daysagainstviolencewomen this year to draw attention to the experience of violence by visibly Muslim women*, which has increased significantly since the terrorist attack. Show civil courage and sign @blackvoicesvolksbegehren because to solve structural problems, political measures are needed.

#blm #blacklivesmatter #feminism #feminist #againstracism #againstislamophobia #endviolenceagainstwomen #endviolence #orangetheworld

Translation picture: The struggle of Muslim women against violence is twofold. On the one hand, they are combating the well-known violence against women: Domestic violence, sexual violence, and sexist discrimination. We share this struggle with all women. In addition to this, we also experience racist violence as Muslim women, often as visible Muslim women.

Translation picture: I oppose all rhetoric and attitudes that make the elimination of violence through behavioural change the task of those affected. Fight violence against women. Always. Everywhere. Without exception.

2.3 ZARA Counseling Center #GegenHassimNetz

Snapshot taken from the website <https://zara.or.at/en/beratungsstellen> [retrieved 2022/02/22]

3. Citizen communication

3.1 Burschenschaft Hysteria

Snapshot taken from Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/BurschenschaftHysteria> [published 2019/01/25, retrieved 2022/02/22]

Translation picture: Too beautiful for a duelling scar. Against the disfigurement of our men.

Translation caption: It's prom season again! That exciting time for men when they get to dress up and we proudly present them. Unfortunately, a new-fashioned trend of self-disfigurement is rampant among particularly sensitive young boys – confused men carve scars into each other's delicate cheeks to prove an allegedly endangered "masculinity". The fraternity Hysteria therefore appeals to all women to watch out for the following signs of this moral and aesthetic neglect in their men and to prevent participation in so-called "male bonding societies":

- 1) tendency to sad thoughts, corners of the mouth pulled downwards
- 2) lack of interest in babies and small children

- 3) consumption of alcohol and tobacco cigarettes
- 4) bizarre dress-up meetings with colourful ribbons and caps beyond the carnival season.
- 5) retarded imaginative vocabulary, conspicuous tendency to garrulousness.
- 6) galloping physical senescence (impotence!)

Intervene resolutely! We will not let our handsome men be disfigured. They are too beautiful for a duelling scar!

Finland

Figure 1 (Ylilauta, 2022).

Vakoojat ovat olleet hölmistyneitä siitä, että sodan raivotessa Euroopassa turvallisuusammattialaisia käsketään keskittymään esimerkiksi "oikeiden" pronomiinien käyttöön, jotta transut eivät loukkaantuisi.

Rappiokulttuuri 4.3.2022 klo 09:53

"Decay culture"

Britannian kansallisen turvallisuuden koneistoa ollaan päivittämässä 2020-luvulle.

Figure 2 (Partisaani, 2022).

Figure 3 (pseudonymised).

Figure 4, screenshot from March 2022 (Kirkon ulkomaanapu, 2022).

Figure 5 (Diakonissalaitos 2018).

keskusrikopoliisi Keskusrikopoliisi · 2020-11-12
 Takaisinkelaus ei toimi oikeassa elämässä. Mieti, ennen kuin jaat. #krp
 #poliisi
 original sound - Keskusrikopoliisi

Figure 6, screenshot from March 2022 (Keskusrikopoliisi, 2020).

Figure 7, screenshot from March 2022 (Tympeät tytöt, 2021).

Figure 8 (Pikakahvimegirl 2020).

Figure 9 (pseudonymised).

3.2 #fensterparade and #fensterparade2020

Snapshot taken from Instagram <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/fensterparade/> [retrieved 2022/02/22]

#fensterparade2020

504 Beiträge

Folgen

Top-Beiträge

Snapshot taken from Instagram <https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/fensterparade2020/>
[retrieved 2022/02/22]

3.3 Dariadaria

Snapshot taken from Instagram <https://www.instagram.com/dariadaria/> [published 2021/09/03, retrieved 2022/02/22]

Translation text: Thank you to the 160 people who made today special. It was a beautiful, relaxed, liberated and self-determined day that I will never forget. Thank you to everyone off- and online who made a statement today against objectification, discrimination, and sexism towards FLINT. The discourse does not end here and it will not end for a long time. We want to be heard, seen, and understood, even if there is still a long way ahead. Thank you for your solidarity, support and being.

France

Fig. 1: Marine Le Pen on feminism

Fig. 2: A comment on "neo-feminism"

Fig. 3: A comment on feminism

Fig. 4: A comment on "neo-fascism"

Fig. 5: A comment about Le Pen

Fig. 6: Comments on feminism

Fig. 7: A comment on Le Pen's feminist views

Fig. 8: Far right critique of Le Pen

Fig. 9: Le Pen: Combative but not arrogant

Eric Zemmour
@ZemmourEric

...

#Mila : À chaque fois qu'il y a l'islam en jeu, les féministes se carapotent. Elles sont très fortes pour insulter le patriarcat, qui n'existe plus depuis longtemps, mais quand il y a une vraie menace sur une jeune femme, alors là il n'y a plus personne.

#Facealinfo

Translate Tweet

7:05 PM · Jun 22, 2021 · Twitter for Android

1,015 Retweets 40 Quote Tweets 3,316 Likes

Fig. 10: The young with Zemmour

Fig. 11: Comments on Zemmour

Fig. 12: Zemmour on feminism and violence

June 7, 2021

PAPACITO 🇷🇺 🇧🇪

Pour les retardataires, Youtube a censuré la vidéo suite à la pression médiatique bolchevique

Voici la sauvegarde <https://t.me/infocomptoir/14443>

Telegram

Infos-Comptoir

Le gauchisme est-il pare balles ? PAPACITO feat CODE RHEINO

La vidéo backup (drôle en plus)

8821 18:54

ons.

Fig. 13: Papacito – boxer

Fig. 14: Papacito – knight

Fig. 15: Papacito – fighter

Fig. 16: Papacito – soldier

Fig. 17: Papacito – carnivore

Fig. 18: Papacito in uniform

Fig. 19: Papacito with weapons

Fig. 20: Papacito: execution of a mannequin

Fig. 21: Papacito: stabbing a mannequin

Fig. 22: Papacito: "Purely scientific"

Fig. 23: Papacito on the left

Fig. 24: Papacito on vaccines

Fig. 25: Papacito on the far-right

Osez le féminisme ! @osezlefeminisme · Mar 7

#Feministometre #8mars #OsezLegalite2022 : Qui défend les droits des femmes ?
 Nous avons analysé, comparé, décortiqué les programmes et des discours des [candidat.es](https://www.candidat.es)

FÉMINISTOMÈTRE

Est-ce que les candidat.es à la présidentielle 2022 défendent les droits des femmes ?

DÉCRYPTE LES PROGRAMMES DES CANDIDAT.ES !

On a comparé pour vous les programmes, discours, bilans des candidat.es à la présidentielle en matière d'engagement féministe !

JEAN-LUC MELENCHON	ANNE HIDALGO	FABIEN ROUSSEL	PHILIPPE POUTOU	YANNICK JADOT EMMANUEL MACRON	VALÉRIE PÉCRÉSSE	NATHALIE ARTHAUX	NICOLAS DUPONT-AIGNAN	MARINE LE PEN	ÉRIC ZEMMOUR
FÉMINISTE		PLUTÔT FÉMINISTE	FEMINISM WASHING	PAS FÉMINISTE			MISOGYNE		

171 1,350 1,526

Fig. 26: Féministomètre

Osez le féminisme ! @osezlefeeminisme · Mar 7

...

#Lepen : misogynie

#Feministometre #8mars #OsezLegalite2022

Instrumentalisation des droits des femmes à des fins racistes (mesures contre les femmes étrangères, obsession sur le voile...).

Contre la loi sur la prostitution qu'elle qualifie de "moraliste".

Zéro parité.

Osez le féminisme

DÉCRYPTE LES CANDIDAT.ES À LA PRÉSIDENTIELLE 2022

MARINE LE PEN

Marine Le Pen évoque les droits des femmes uniquement lorsque cela sert son agenda politique raciste. Ses prises de position stigmatisent sur les prétendues "VIG de confort", son soutien de longue date à des dirigeants masculinistes et son programme sur l'immigration qui nuirait gravement aux femmes étrangères résidant en France en font un danger réel pour les droits des femmes.

Misogynie

Milieu actuel des femmes étrangères dans les commerces :

- L'agacement plus facile les vis-à-vis des clients
- Les personnes contraintes pour vestiges vestiaires fermé
- Risque d'une émigration au filer des crises et déficiences sécuritaires

Économie :

- Déconjonction et instrumentalisation de l'éducation adultes handicapés en (IAH).
- Réévaluation des salaires à des personnes et les salarient à l'aune de leur travail.
- Multiplication par deux du soutien aux mères isolées et renforcement des contrôles pour éviter les fraudes : une mesure à priori féministe mais en réalité stigmatisante.
- Suppression de aides sociales et de l'aide médicale d'Etat (AME) pour les femmes étrangères.

Santé :

- Stigmatisation des femmes qui ont recours à des prétendues "VIG de confort", opposition à l'allongement des congés.

Éducation :

- Vision conservatrice de l'école qui ne se limite aux "fondamentaux" : non sur l'éducation à la sexualité.
- Réévaluation des salaires des enseignantes.

Prostitution / GPA :

- Opposition à la loi abolitionniste de 2016 qualifiée de "moraliste". Contre les aides pour les femmes étrangères en situation de prostitution.
- Renforcement de l'interdiction de la GPA.

Bilan masculiniste :

- À l'Assemblée Nationale et au Parlement Européen, elle a voté contre toutes les lois renforçant les droits des femmes (PPL, VIG, égalité salariale...)
- Instrumentalisation du féminisme à des fins anti-immigration et racistes, comme en témoignent son obsession de l'interdiction du voile dans l'espace public. Son combat pour la "laïcité" se fait par le contrôle des corps des femmes.
- Soutien à des dirigeants masculinistes : Viktor Orbán, Vladimir Poutine, masculinistes notables.

Forme du programme :

Pas d'écriture inclusive, elle souhaite d'ailleurs interdire celle-ci.

Communication et campagne :

Zéro parité dans la gare rapprochée de son équipe de campagne avec 7 hommes et aucune femme.

6

39

37

Fig. 27: Misogynist Le Pen

Osez le féminisme ! @osezlefeminisme · Mar 7

#Zemmour : misogynne masculiniste

#Feministometre #8mars #OsezLegalite2022

Candidat dangereux défendant l'infériorité des femmes, et le droit des hommes à accéder aux corps des femmes (viols, prostitution...)

Politique familiale réactionnaire.

Accusation d'agressions sexuelles

DÉCRYPTE LES CANDIDAT.ES À LA PRÉSIDENTIELLE 2022

ÉRIC ZEMMOUR

Éric Zemmour s'attaque en permanence aux femmes et prône la supériorité masculine ainsi que la culture du viol. Poursuivi pour apologie de la haine raciale, considérant que les migrants sont des "violeurs", il instrumentalise les droits des femmes à des fins racistes. Son programme haineux et masculiniste nuirait gravement aux droits des femmes.

Misogyne

Économie :

- Prime de 10 000 € par enfant et de 2000 € par adulte ; c'est une politique néolibérale conservatrice, ce budget fera à nouveau affluer des milliards pour des mesures d'épave comme l'alargissement du congé parental.
- Suppression du plafond de ressources des allocations familiales et doublement du plafond du quotient familial mesurant pendant les années à venir au foyer et favorisant les mariages aisés au détriment des mariages non imposés, notamment les mariages précaires pour lesquels aucune revalorisation n'est prévue.
- Suppression des ménages sociaux pour les étrangers ; cette mesure raciste aggraverait la précarité des femmes étrangères.

Santé :

- Abrogation de la PMA pour tous.
- Contre l'élargissement des délais de IVG.
- Suppression de l'aide médicale d'État (AME) : cela mettrait gravement en danger la santé des femmes migrantes sans titre de séjour, notamment lorsqu'elles sont enceintes, cette mesure est contraire à leurs droits fondamentaux.
- Rien sur la individualisation de l'allocation adulte handicapé (AAH).

Éducation :

Défendre farouchement face à la pression des « théologues féministes antiracistes, LGBT ».

Prostitution / GPA :

- Signataire de la tribune des "943 salauds" en 2015 qui réclament de pouvoir accéder librement aux corps des femmes par la prostitution.
- Opposition à la GPA.

Réforme des institutions :

Contre les lois sur la parité.

Bilan masculiniste :

- Accusations d'agressions sexuelles au cours de 15 dernières années.
- Instrumentalisation du féminisme à des fins antisémitiques et racistes : « Les féministes approuvent, par leur silence avec les islamistes et les gauchistes sont les plus grandes ennemies des femmes ».
- Manifestation des valeurs masculines : « Dans une société traditionnelle, l'appâté sexuel des hommes va de pair avec le pouvoir : les femmes sont le but et le butin de tout homme digne qui ose se griser dans la société. » (Le Suicide français)

Forme du programme :

Pas d'écriture inclusive.

Communication et campagne :

É. Zemmour est pratiquement au niveau zéro de la parole avec environ 6 femmes pour 50 hommes dans son équipe de campagne. La stratégie de communication est à l'ancienne.

29 60 56

Fig. 28: Misogynist Zemmour

Apr 14

Replying to @osezlefeminisme

vous n'avez pas le monopole du féminisme les mondialistes. vous ne représentez que vous même, et plutot le mondialisme que le féminisme d'ailleurs.

Apr 6

Replying to @osezlefeminisme

Marine Le Pen, une femme, est misogynne? C'est ridicule. Complètement idiot. Et je ne voterai pas pour elle.

Mar 31

Replying to @osezlefeminisme

Zemmour président 🇫🇷

Fig. 29: Comments on Zemmour's feministometre

Inter-LGBT @InterLGBT · Apr 19

5 jours avant le 2ème tour de l' #electionpresidentielle2022 on vous rappelle en quoi l'extrême droite est à l'opposée de nos valeurs et contre les droits des femmes.

#PasUneVoixPourLePen dimanche prochain !

Fig. 30: Inter-LGBT 1

Fig. 31: Inter-LGBT 1.1¹

¹ “The extreme right and the right to abortion is:

‘Aborting three or four times in a row should not weigh in financial terms on the national community, at the time where one in three French do not take proper care of themselves’ (Marine Le Pen, France 2, 2012).

‘If I have a budgetary choice to make between not reimbursing abortion which is an act that can be avoided, given that anyway there are many means of contraception in our country, and to have to

Fig. 32: Inter-LGBT 1.²

reimburse acts which cannot be avoided and which allow French that suffer to take care of themselves, I would choose the second option' (Marine Le Pen, TF1, March 2012)."

² "The extreme right and [the use of] ART for everyone is:

[The extreme right] voted against the bioethics law, which includes a section opening ART to lesbian and single women (June 2021).

'Setting up a legal lie inscribing in marble what remains a biological impossibility is not protecting the child, nor protecting their rights. The child is the fruit of a father and a mother. A child has the right to have a father' (Marine Le Pen, National Assembly, September 2019).

'Me it's rather Manif pour tous [Manifestation for all: a group of French political associations organizing demonstrations against the use of ART for all] (...). I actually paraded in the street against this bill, against marriage for all but more for the openness to ART and surrogacy which this bill entailed' (Jordan Bardella, i24News, April 2018).

Fig. 33: Inter-LGBT 1.3³

³ "The extreme right and [the use of] ART for everyone is:

'Unlike most homosexual couples who ask only discretion, this gay *communautarisme* [for the meaning of this term in France, see Sawyer and Zinigrad, 2021b] claims, under the pretext of 'equality', a true superiority: an alleged 'right to a child' despite a sexuality excluding procreation.

This cannot and should not be legitimated by the state. At all times and in every place, marriage is the institution that protects the union of a man and a woman, the only one able to transmit life and educate children.

We also denounce the 'gender theory' which tends to believe that sex is chosen. The National Front [former name of the National Rally party] defends this only viable model of a natural and 'sustainable' society. Give meaning to life!' (Bruno Gollnisch, June 2013, National Rally website).

Féministes Insoumis-es @Phiministe · Mar 16, 2017

"Arrêtez avec votre féminisme, les femmes sont déjà = des hommes !"
Ouais c'est vrai que la liste n'est pas longue ... #féministesinsoumis

↻ 26

♥ 13

Fig. 34: Féministes Insoumis-es 1

Féministes Insoumis-es Retweeted

Danielle Simonnet ✓
@SimonnetDeputee

Un prêche homophobe, anti avortement, comparant l'avortement à la Shoah, sur @franceculture, une radio du service public ! Ce n'est pas aux radios et TV du service public de diffuser les cultes, qui plus est des intégristes, ça doit cesser !

[Translate Tweet](#)

marianne.net

France Culture : quand le service public diffuse une messe catholique intégrist...
Ce dimanche 15 juillet, la radio de service public a livré son antenne pendant près d'une heure à Mgr Jean-Pierre Cattenoz, qui multiplie de longue date des ...

12:50 AM · Jul 19, 2018 · Twitter for iPhone

84 Retweets · 7 Quote Tweets · 107 Likes

Fig. 35: Féministes Insoumis-es 2

Plan de combat et difficile, plus le langage est belic

████████████████████ · Jul 19, 2018 ...
Replying to @SimonnetDeputee @simonnet2 and @franceculture
Quelle honte... J'espère que plainte va être déposée.
1 1 1 1 1

████████████████████ · Jul 19, 2018 ...
Il faut faire un signalement sur le site du csa
1 1 1 1 1

████████████████████ · Jul 19, 2018 ...
Replying to @SimonnetDeputee @simonnet2 and @franceculture
Il faut faire des signalements au @csaudiovisuel !
1 1 1 1 1

ACRO MISSI · Jul 19, 2018 ...
Replying to @SimonnetDeputee @simonnet2 and @franceculture
Elle est ou la laïcité?
1 1 1 1 1

Fig. 36: Comments on Féministes Insoumis-es

Fig. 37: Comments on *Féministes Insoumis-es 2*

Fig. 38: Comments on *Féministes Insoumis-es 3*

Fig. 39: #LesPrincessesOntDesPoils 1

Fig. 40: #LesPrincessesOntDesPoils 2

Fig. 41: #LesPrincessesOntDesPoils 2.1

Fig. 42: #LesPrincessesOntDesPoils 2.2

Fig. 43: #LesPrincessesOntDesPoils 2.3

Fig. 44: A comment on #LesPrincessesOntDesPoils

Fig. 47: Angèle

Fig. 48: Tariq Ramadan 1

Yann Le Mercier
@YannLemerrier14

Replying to @EQUINOXE_2022 and @TariqRamadan

Finally the serial rapist [@TariqRamadan](#) goes to the assizes [#MeToo](#) [#balancetonporc](#)
[@nytimes](#) [@washingtonpost](#) [@carlottagall](#)
[@ElianPeltier](#) [@jameskmcauley](#)

BFM TV. TV RADIO

TARIQ RAMADAN: LE PARQUET DE PARIS DEMANDE LES ASSISES POUR DES VIOLS SUR QUATRE FEMMES

Le 12/07/2022 à 13:43

FAITES ENTREZ L'ACCUSÉ

Dans ce dossier, Tariq Ramadan a d'abord nié avoir eu des relations sexuelles extraconjugales avant de reconnaître des "relations de domination", rudes mais "consenties".

4:58 PM · Aug 3, 2022 · Twitter for Android

1 Quote Tweet

🗨️ 🔄 ❤️ ⬇️ ⬆️

Fig. 49: Tariq Ramadan 2

Fig. 53: Comments on the Ramadan affair

Fig. 54: #BalanceTonPorc 2

Fig. 56: #SciencesPorcs 1

Fig. 55: #BalanceTonPorc 2

Fig. 58: Comments on #SciencesPorcs

Fig. 59: SciencesPorcs 3

Germany

Appendix 1. Media objects by agents of radicalisation in Germany

1.1. Representation of traditional gender roles by German far-right

1.1.1. AfD electoral poster for 2017 federal elections

Source: https://www.afd.de/wp-content/uploads/sites/111/2017/07/2017-07-20_afd-btw_faltblatt_familie-traditionell.pdf

1.1.2. Post by Junge Alternative and comments (the youth organisation of AfD).

Source: <https://www.instagram.com/p/CO5iIVbtqxh/>

Comment 1.1.2.1

██████████ Белые семьи
должны быть многодетными!

35 нед. Ответить

Comment 1.1.2.2

██████████ Freiheitliche Nation.
Außer du bist homosexuell,
Ausländer, Frau, Moslem, oder
einfach kein Arier.

35 нед. "Нравится": 15 Ответить ...

Comment 1.1.2.3

██████████ 1,2
„Kinder“ pro deutsche Familie-Die
Globalisten,Kommunisten freuen
sich!

35 нед. Ответить ...

Comment 1.1.2.4

██████████ Schön zu sehen das es
noch eine Partei gibt die sich gegen
diesen ganzen Gender Gagga Mist
und Gender Mainstreaming
ausspricht! AfD

35 нед. "Нравится": 4 Ответить ...

Comment 1.1.2.5

██████████
@yes_for_democracy Die Glorifizierung findet zunehmend in öffentlichen Händen statt. Es werden bewusst immer häufiger homosexuelle Paare gezeigt die fröhlich durchs Leben gehn. Sie werden fortlaufend in Werbungen beispielsweise gezeigt. Tinder und der DFB als große Namen springen mit auf den Zug auf. Dagegen hat doch auch keiner etwas. Aber das ständige in den Mittelpunkt stellen von Familienstrukturen aufgrund von Gender und LGBTQI*+ ist Schwachwinn.

bisherige Integration und Assimilation scheitert. Während muslimische Einwanderer mehr Kinder zeugen als nötig und deutsche Familien weniger als nötig werden wir in den nächsten Jahren einen enormen Kulturwandel erleben. Mit mehr muslimischen Einfluss und Wirkung in unserer Gesellschaft verlieren wir deutsche Werte und Stück für Stück unsere Kultur während in muslimischen Nationen Menschen gegen den Islam kämpfen. Deshalb sind höhere Geburtenraten ein

Ja und darf ich wegen einem Punkt eine Partei nichtmehr unterstützen? Ich bin auch für Ehe für alle aber nur wegen einem Punkt der nicht übereinstimmt muss ich doch nicht meine Partei aufgeben oder haben Sie 100% Übereinstimmung mit ihrer Partei? Das wir mehr Kinder brauchen ist klar wenn wir uns den demographischen Wandel ansehen. Wir haben einen enormen Zug von Migration in den letzten Jahren gesehen. Und die bisherige Integration und

Geburtenraten ein wichtiges Mittel um deutschlands Kultur weiter zu erben. Einer der vielen Gründe neben Wirtschaftskraft.

Comment 1.1.2.6

@and.e17 inwiefern werden Familienstrukturen immer häufiger aufgrund von Gender oder LGBTQ+ in den Mittelpunkt gestellt? Ich bin im übrigen nicht parteipolitisch aktiv, habe aber trotzdem meine Ansichten. Und meine Ansicht sagt: Eine Partei die etwas so fundamentales wie die gleichgeschlechtliche Ehe ablehnt ist für mich nicht wählbar. Ja wir hatten Migration in den letzten Jahren, war nie anders. Das ist auch nichts schlimmes.

„deutsche Werte und Kultur“ sind. Und Menschen in muslimischen Nationen kämpfen nicht gegen den Islam sondern gegen Islamisten (kleiner aber wichtiger Unterschied). Ihre ganze Argumentation erinnert sehr an Stereotypen und ein biologisches Menschenbild, das die Wissenschaft längst widerlegt hat.

ist auch nichts schlimmes. Integration hat trotzdem relativ gut funktioniert, muss jedoch noch verbessert werden. Assimilation hingegen ist verfassungswidrig und daher auch nicht wünschenswert. Und wieso 5 Millionen muslimische Menschen in Deutschland angeblich unsere „Werte und Kultur“ bedrohen kann ich beim besten Willen nicht erkennen. Zumal mir bislang keiner erklären konnte was genau „deutsche Werte und Kultur“ sind. Und Menschen in muslimischen Nationen

1.1.3. AfD Munich greetings to commemorate World Man's Day

Source: <https://www.instagram.com/p/CV0FW2ZslQV/>

1.2. Attacking "gender mainstreaming" by far-right

1.2.1. AfD meme ridiculing the gendered language

◀ ähm.. mit "sie" was ist daran falsch? ▶

ICH BIN NICHT BINÄR UND TRANSGENDER ALSO HEISST DAS "SIER" UND DU HAST BAHNHOF NICHT GEGENDERT DU SEXIST. BIST DU STOLZ DARAUF SO EIN SCHLECHTER MENSCH ZU SEIN?

◀ ich will doch nur zum Bahnhof ▶

BAHNHOF*INNEN WAS IST MIT DIR? alle Männer sind gleich.. und bist du eigentlich für BLM???? ODER BIST DU EIN RASSIST WEIL DU HAST NICHT GESAGT DU BIST DAFÜR HALLO?

HALLO bleib hier du sexistischer Rassist! UNTERSTÜTZT DU EIGENTLICH LGBTQ DU HAST NÄMLICH NIRGENDS EINE REGENBOGEN-FLAGGE DU HOMOPHOBES MÄNNLICHES ARSCHLOCH

◀

hey weißt du wo es zum Bahnhof geht?

klar einfach die Straße lang und dann nach rechts

Comment 1.2.1.1

████████ digga ihr denkt euch
szenarien aus, die so nie
vorgekommen sind und fuckt euch
darüber ab, ihr seid so lächerlich 🤔

3 нед. "Нравится": 15

Comment 1.2.1.2

████████ Traurig zu sehen, wie das
Land langsam aber sicher in den
Abgrund schweift.

45 нед. "Нравится": 24

Comment 1.2.1.3

████████ Das traurige ist, dass
Family guy mal so etwas als Spaß in
einer Folge hatte... Diese
Gesellschaft ist nicht zu retten

45 нед. "Нравится": 6

Comment 1.2.1.4

████████ Alter das ist ja an mimimi
dummheit nicht mehr zu übertreffen
😏😏😏

45 нед. "Нравится": 7

1.2.2. Junge Freiheit cartoon

Source:

<https://www.facebook.com/jungefreiheit/photos/a.431214844941/10158364758884942/>

Comment 1.2.2.1

██████████
Dafür sicher nicht. Aber was Ihr könnt ist gut das Opfer spielen, seid Ihr aber nicht.

Comment 1.2.2.2

██████████
Junge junge wer den scheiß ernst nimmt und glaubt das hat irgendwas mit der Wahrheit zu tun der war noch nie im Fussball Stadion.
Das schöne ist aber das sich gleich die möchtegern verteidiger des Abendlandes bestätigt fühlen 🤔🤔

Comment 1.2.2.3

Sollen die Fans künftig die Nationalmannschaft mit "Vielfalt vor, noch ein Tor" anfeuern? Spielt die Bundesliga künftig anstatt um die deutsche Meisterschaft um den Toleranz Pokal?

Нравится Ответить Показать перевод
2 г. Отредактировано

... wenn es nach den Bescheuerten, Gutmenschen und Grünen geht bestimmt.

Нравится Ответить
Показать перевод 2 г.

Was für zwei dumme Kommentare

Нравится Ответить
Показать перевод 2 г.

Comment 1.2.2.4

Ich war immer ein glühender Anhänger der deutschen Nationalmannschaft. Bis zu dem Zeitpunkt wo das Team in "Die Mannschaft" umbenannt wurde, das erste mal ein Trikot ohne Nationalfarben getragen wurde, sich Spieler wie Özil breit machten und am Ende die ganzen Regenbogenflaggen die ständig geschwungen werden. Dieser Fussballverein dient nur noch als politisches Instrument der ganzen "Deutschland ist bunt" Bewegung und beleidigt meine Intelligenz.

Comment 1.2.2.5

Hast du schon mal ausgerechnet wie hoch die Kosten von Gewaltdemos der Linken, Grünen und SPDler sind und wie groß ihr Schaden am Lande durch Ihre Willkommenspolitik.

Comment 1.2.2.6

Hat eigentlich mal jemand ausgerechnet, was die Hooligan-Gewalt in unseren Fußball-Stadien den Steuerzahler kosten? Was genau ist an diesen Leuten eigentlich "patriotisch"?

Comment 1.2.2.7

██████████
██████████ wenn
Du dafür die Tatsache
akzeptierst daß von dem
Demozug der normalen
Bürger, die tatsächlich
Angst um ihre Sicherheit
nachts beim Chemnitzer
Stadtfest hatten, vielleicht
5% Rechtsextreme waren.
Die ständig von Türken
und der Antifa provoziert
worden sind. So daß es zu
einer "Menschenjagd"
kam, die eine Strecke von
25m lang war.
Daß diese Bürger recht
haben sieht man ja jetzt
daran daß das Chemnitzer
Stadtfest wegen
Sicherheitsbedenken
dieses Jahr abgesagt
wurde! 😞
Übrigens, die "Gejagten",
zwei arabische Jungs, die
laut Zeugen vorher
extreme provozierende

extreme provozierende
Gesten gemacht hatten,
hatten bei 30° kurze
Hosen und dafür aber
Handschuhe an. Komisch,
oder? Gerüchteweise sind
solche Handschuhe mit
Sand gefüllt und die
werden zum absichtlichen
Prügeln verwendet!

Comment 1.2.2.8

██████████
ich Frage mich was so eine
dämlich Karikatur soll.
Was hat Sexualität mit
Deutschland zu tun
homosexuelle Menschen
können genau so „ Deutsch,,
sein wie alle anderen .
Ganz ganz schwach und eines
echten Deutschen nicht
würdig.

Appendix 2. Media objects by stakeholders of de-radicalisation in Germany

2.1. Gender Dings campaign poster

2.2. SHEROES Fund

Source: <https://www.facebook.com/AmadeuAntonioStiftung/posts/10159240047518256>

Comment 2.2.1

Bei solchen ungelenk-ideologischen Sprach-Mätzchen wie "herstory" und "Sheroes", bei denen manche glauben, Realität mit Sprach-Akrobatik verändern zu können, springe ich ab.

Ich bin seit meiner Pubertät Feminist - -- weitestgehend im Sinne Simone de Beauvoirs.

Mit dem Feminismus der gender theory und des 3-wave - und intersektionellen Feminismus habe ich explizit nichts zu tun.

Und deren Sprachvorgaben und Sprach-Spielereien lehne ich ebenso explizit ab.

Und werde sie bei jeder Gelegenheit verspotten.

Für mich hat dies im harmloseren Falle pubertär-pseudo-progressive Züge , im schlechten Falle ist es jedoch der Versuch der totalitären Indoktrination mit Neu-Sprech a la "1984".

Нравится Ответить Показать перевод 48 нед. Отредактировано 16

Comment 2.2.2

Автор

Amadeu Antonio Stiftung ✓

Spannend wie hier anbedrachts realer Bedrohungen einer Frau durch Rechtsextreme Begriffsdiskussionen geführt werden, anstatt sich ohne wenn und aber mit der Betroffenen zu solidarisieren. Dieses Privileg muss man sich erst sehr hart erarbeitet haben. Wie man Sprache so viel Bedeutung zumessen kann, vielleicht beim nächsten Mal mehr praktische Solidarität als performative Kapriolen.

Нравится Ответить Показать перевод 48 нед. 37

Comment 2.2.3

Amadeu Antonio Stiftung Wenn diese Wortklaubereien so bedeutungslos sind, kann man sie ja auch sein lassen, gell. Interessant, wie hier Rechtsextremismus verharmlost wird! Sehr unwürdig.

Нравится Ответить Показать перевод 48 нед. 2

Comment 2.2.4

Amadeu Antonio Stiftung Wo nehmen sie in dieser Diskussion schon wieder den Rechtsextremismus her? Dieses Totschlagargument dass jede weitere Diskussion unterbinden und den Diskussionspartner in eine "Rechte" Ecke zwingen soll zeigt wie wenig Sie an der echten Aufarbeitung interessiert sind. Sie betreiben einfach nur ekelhaftesten Populismus. Jedes ihrer Worte verdreht die "normale" Sprache und dann ist Ihre Argumentation dass man der Sprache nicht soviel Bedeutung beimessen sollte?! Das ist doch wohl ein Witz! (So nun aber Feuer von allen Seiten, kann ja wohl nicht sein dass jemand widerspricht)

Нравится Ответить Показать перевод 48 нед. Отредактировано

Comment 2.2.5

Sie hörten den zeitgenössischen männlichen antifeministischen Sprechautomat.

Нравится Ответить Показать перевод 48 нед. Отредактировано

2.3. "Miss and Mister Homophobia" poll ("Enough is enough" NGO)

[Facebook](#)

Comment 2.3.1

Mich irritiert, dass mehr Leute Angela Merkel ihre Stimme gegeben haben als Alexander Gauland und Beatrix von Storch. Ernsthaft? Die Frau mag zwar jetzt keine Befürworterin sein, aber irgendwie scheinen jetzt auch viele Schwule auf die "Danke Merkel!"-Sache einzugehen und hören damit eigentlich auf genau die homophoben Idioten, gegen die es eigentlich geht.

Comment 2.3.2

Sorry, aber Miss geht gar nicht, das ist wiederum sexistisch oder würdet ihr etwa auf Deutsch Fräulein und Herr Homophobie sagen? Neutral hieße es Ms. und Mr., wenn ihr schon im binären Schema bleiben wollt.

Comment 2.3.3

Zwei Homosexuelle zu "Miss und Mister Homophobia" wählen.
Makes sense!

Das zeigt wie dumm ihr Linken seid und dass ihr in der politischen Debatte nichts verloren habt! 😏

Appendix 3. Media objects by ordinary users against radicalisation in Germany

3.1. Tweets by activist and blogger Andreas Kemper

3.1.1. Tweet in response to terrorist attack in Norway, October 2021

Source: [AndreasKemper on Twitter](#)

Comment 3.1.1.1

Comment 3.1.1.2

 Oct 15, 2021 ...

Bei einem islamistischen Anschlag ist das Problem, laut Kemper, toxische Männlichkeit.
Die Anschläge von Hanau und Halle waren für ihn allerdings ganz klar rechtsextremistisch motiviert. Erklärt mir mal jemand diese Gehirn-Akrobatik?

 AndreasKemper @AndreasKemper · Oct 14, 2021

Ich poste seit Jahren bei solchen Anschlägen:
Das Problem heißt #Männlichkeit.

Das ist die kleinste Gemeinsamkeit im Täter*innen-Profil. Es sind fast immer Männer. (Ich denke nicht, dass das irgendwas mit "biologischer" Männlichkeit zu tun hat) [tagesspiegel.de/gesellschaft/p...](https://www.tagesspiegel.de/gesellschaft/p...)
#Kongsberg

4 9 58 ↑

Comments 3.1.1.3

 Oct 17, 2021 ...

Und ich dachte "biologische" Männlichkeit wäre nur ein soziales Konstrukt nach heutiger Sozialkunde 🤔
Ja was denn nun?
Vielleicht doch nur Religion?

 AndreasKemper @AndreasKemper · Oct 14, 2021

Ich poste seit Jahren bei solchen Anschlägen:
Das Problem heißt #Männlichkeit.

Das ist die kleinste Gemeinsamkeit im Täter*innen-Profil. Es sind fast immer Männer. (Ich denke nicht, dass das irgendwas mit "biologischer" Männlichkeit zu tun hat) [tagesspiegel.de/gesellschaft/p...](https://www.tagesspiegel.de/gesellschaft/p...)
#Kongsberg

0 0 0 0

 Oct 16, 2021 ...

Ich übersetze: Der Islam ist so unschuldig und friedlich wie ein Hasenbaby. Allah ist übrigens eine Frau. Jawohl, eine waschechte Frau.

 AndreasKemper @AndreasKemper · Oct 14, 2021

Ich poste seit Jahren bei solchen Anschlägen:
Das Problem heißt #Männlichkeit.

Das ist die kleinste Gemeinsamkeit im Täter*innen-Profil. Es sind fast immer Männer. (Ich denke nicht, dass das irgendwas mit "biologischer" Männlichkeit zu tun hat) [tagesspiegel.de/gesellschaft/p...](https://www.tagesspiegel.de/gesellschaft/p...)
#Kongsberg

1 0 2 0

Comments 3.1.1.4

 [Redacted] Oct 14, 2021 ...
Replying to [@AndreasKemper](#)
Das Geschlecht eines Menschen, welches er mit der Hälfte der Menschheit teilt kann wohl nie der KLEINSTE gemeinsame Nenner sein (außer man versteht das Konzept nicht)

1

 AndreasKemper [@AndreasKemper](#) - Oct 14, 2021 ...
Was hat die Gruppe der Attentäter*innen (Anokiäufer*innen, Mass-Shooter, rechtsterroristische oder islamistische Terrorist*innen, Attentäter aus dem Incel-Milieu...) an Merkmalen gemeinsam, was die Gruppe der Nicht-Attentäter*innen nicht hat?

2

 [Redacted] Oct 14, 2021 ...
Replying to [@AndreasKemper](#)
Sorry Herr Kemper, aber das ist eine blödsinnige Argumentation, da Männlichkeit auch ihre Diversität besitzt und deren Schnittmengen dann wiederum auf biologische Aspekte deuten lassen. Entweder spezifizieren Sie auf der kulturellen Ebene nach Form(en) oder wechseln die These.

1

 AndreasKemper [@AndreasKemper](#) - Oct 14, 2021 ...
Ich habe das doch schon längst spezifiziert.
andreas Kemper.org/2020/05/03/cra...

1

3.1.2. Tweet commenting on a declaration by Bundeswehr soldiers planning to march against the government, December 2021

"Der Kampf in mir ist gekämpft" So klang auch der faschistische Fanatismus von Goebbels und Hitler. Wir haben es hier mit soldatischen Männlichkeiten zu tun, die den Schritt in die apokalyptische Männlichkeit machen.

[Translate Tweet](#)

Robert Andreasch @robertandreasch · Dec 30, 2021

Brandgefährlich: Die #Bundeswehr-Soldaten Daniel Futschik (Kaserne #Euskirchen) und Andreas Oberauer (#BadReichenhall) haben öffentlich angekündigt, den Kampf gegen die Regierung zu beginnen. Oberauer hat in einem Video ein "Ultimatum" gestellt, das morgen um 16.00 Uhr abläuft.

[Show this thread](#)

The screenshot shows a tweet thread with a video and text. The video is titled "30. Dezember" and shows a man in a military uniform. The text in the thread includes:

- Hier die Freiwilligenmeldung des OFW Oberauer,**
- Hier der Aufruf des OFW Oberauer,** an jeden wehrhaften Bürger.
- Artikel 20(4) GG, Widerstand** gegen jeden der es unternimmt
- kann. Vielleicht ein Kampf David gegen Goliath? Wer weiß? Ich für mich weiß allerdings, dass es der richtige und einzige Weg ist, den ich nun zu gehen habe. Nicht für mein Ego. Ich gehe ihn für meine Frau, meine Kinder, meine Eltern, Geschwister, Neffen, Cousins, Freunde und alle Herzensmenschen, die nicht die Kraft, den Mut oder Möglichkeiten haben sich zu wehren. Der Kampf in Mir ist gekämpft, ich habe diesen Weg mit Frieden und Kraft in

12:33 PM · Dec 30, 2021 · Twitter Web App

Comments 3.1.2.1

3.2. TikTok comments

3.2.1. TikTok on sexist statements by AfD politicians

Comments 3.2.1.1

- Disgusting...es gibt einfach keine Entschuldigung dafür die zu wählen !!!

2021-7-26 Responder ♥
177
- Creador**

Eigentlich nicht.. und trotzdem wählen sie so viel... 😞

2021-7-31 Responder ♥
32
- Ja, viele hören nur auf die Parolen ohne wirklich darüber informiert zu sein was die für Grundeinstellungen etc haben. sonst würde die keiner wählen.

2021-8-25 Responder ♥
1

- JessicaB**

Und es gibt Frauen die diese Patel für gut Empfinden, das muss man sich mal überlegen..

2021-8-24 Responder ♥
24
- Frau.Kraft · Creador**

Das kann man sich eigentlich gar nicht ausdenken... das ist so verrückt und dumm. 😞

2021-8-24 Responder ...
♥
9
- JessicaB**

erschreckend finde ich das

2021-8-24 Responder ♥
2

Comments 3.2.1.2

- Das ist doch voll außem Kontext gerissen.

2021-8-31 Responder ♥
12
- Creador**

Na dann mal her mit dem Kontext.

2021-8-31 Responder ♥
9
- Für den Kontext ist derjenige verantwortlich, der zitiert. In dem Fall also DU.

2021-9-5 Responder ...
♥
4

[REDACTED]
 Hauptsache hetzen. Einfach mal die vorherigen Aussagen dazu mit veröffentlicht, dann würde sich vieles klären

 23

2021-7-27 Responder

[REDACTED] **Creador**
 Na dann her damit.

 22

2021-7-27 Responder

Comments 3.2.1.3

[REDACTED]
 Die Haben nur Angst vor der Frau 😞😞

 83

2021-6-20 Responder

Bianca
 Ach wir haben sehr viele Frauen in der Partei 😞

 1

2021-7-27 Responder

[REDACTED] **Creador**
 Und? Ihr habt auch Menschen mit Migrationshintergrund in der Partei und wollt trotzdem, dass nur DE mit DE Vorfahren den DE Pas bekommen.

 3

2021-7-27 Responder

[REDACTED]
 Habt ihr euch mal gemerkt was andere Politiker im Bundestag so von sich geben? Diese „frauenfeindliche“ Partei hat ne SpitzenkandidatIN

 104

2021-6-19 Responder

[REDACTED]
 Traurig das man jetzt so eine Partei versucht zu verteidigen 😞

 35

2021-6-20 Responder

[REDACTED]
 JEDER Politiker benimmt sich im Bundestag komplett daneben & wirft mir Beleidigungen um sich, aber NUR bei der AfD merkt man sich's. Ach komm, hör auf

 27

2021-6-20 Responder

3.2.2 TikTok on Alice Weidel

Comment 3.2.2.1

Der Lehrer: Die Klausur wird einfach.
Die Klausur: Alice Weidel
2021-8-11 Responder 187

Hahaha 😂
2021-8-11 Responder 15

Comment 3.2.2.2

ich glaub die frau wacht manchmal nachts heulend
auf und fragt sich was sie da eigentlich macht
2021-8-11 Responder 45

Comment 3.2.2.3

safe is alice weidel nh spionin von den grünen lol
haha
2021-8-10 Responder 62

Hahahaha Maybe 😂
2021-8-10 Responder 5

Alice Weidel - Der Widerspruch in Person
2021-8-10 Responder 11

Isso
2021-8-10 Responder 1

Hungary

Appendices

Appendix 1: Media objects

<p>252 kedvelés</p> <p>duro_dora_hivatalos_oldal ! Nem tűri a Mi Hazánk, hogy a gyerekeket kitégyék a homoszexuális propagandának már azzal is, hogy a mesekönyvekbe csempészik be az abnormális életformát, ami így hazugság, hiszen a magyar kultúrának nem részei a homoszexuális királyfik. Mai sajtótájékoztatómon megsemmisítettem a homoszexualizmus propagandakönyvét, ami a gyerekek egészséges</p>	<p>Image I</p> <p>Instagram post of MP Dóra Dúró of her press conference, when she publicly shredded the book <i>Fairy Tale for Everyone</i></p>
	<p>Image II</p> <p>The President of the Republic, Katalin Novák features in a YouTube video giving advice to women on how to live fully as a housewife and “not to pursue career like men do”.</p>

Image III

Female MPs in the Hungarian Parliament hold demonstrates against toxic masculinity. One translates: In a moral and mental sense, one cannot be classified as a women, if she does not fulfil the female principium. The other one was a question from a male Fidesz politician to a female opposition MP: Why do you even talk, woman?

Image IV

TikTok videos of young women with the same sound

Image V
 Society for Women NGO's
 TikTok video on abortion with 0
 likes and 0 shares

Image VI
 TikTok video uploaded by
 Budapest Pride

Italy

Appendices

Appendix 1 - Items by Radicalizing Agents (screenshots)

Jürgen With Anderlan/SSB –Facebook

Lega/Matteo Salvini - Twitter

← Tweet

 Matteo Salvini ✓
@matteosalvinimi

Ipocrita, buonista, razzista con gli italiani. Dimettiti!
[#sgonfiaboldrini](#)

3:28 nachm. · 25. Juli 2016 · Twitter Web Client

344 Retweets 53 Zitierte Tweets 703 „Gefällt mir“-Angaben

Comments to Salvini's post:

"communist rich billionaire scumbag cesspool"

"boldrini you represent the garbage of our beautiful Italy resign"

"one who says Muslims are good people look who is talking nonsense between you and me"

"she should go to the muslims"

Lega/Simone Pillon – Facebook

Fratelli d'Italia/Giorgia Meloni-Twitter

Translation of Pillon's post, October 27th, 2021:

"A toast to Italy, which in difficult times knows how to find its best.

A toast to the thousands of people, families, moms, and dads who have animated the squares of the standing sentinels, enduring insults and swearing to watch over freedom of speech, thought, education, and religion.

Here's to our kids being able to grow up free from gender indoctrination.

A big thank you to the thousands of people who prayed for this to happen.

And a big hug to the 20 million families who every day, in silence, make our Italy great.

Still there is hope, for our country.

Still we can resist the ideological invasion of gender, politically corrupt, cancel culture and all the great temptations of individualism and relativism.

A toast also to Mentana⁴ who, in anger, says I am the only one laughing.

In reality there are millions of us, the silent majority, toasting to freedom tonight.

#noddlzan”

Comments to Pillon’s post:

“Here's to the holy long live Christ in his angels and saints hallelujahaa”

“Revelation is long, the wicked and foolish are many, and this is only one battle. But God is with us. And his is the victory!”

Comments to Meloni’s post:

“With this speech he confirms that Islam is more than 600 years behind. Inquisition began in 1478 and Its most renowned inquisitor was Torquemada”

“TERRIFYING ... we need a special law that allows the restriction of the basic rights of these people-beasts and kick them out with permanent ban on re-entry.”

“obviously on the left and from feminists no signal 🙄🙄🙄🙄🙄”

“Where are the strawmen of hypocritical and shitty communist feminism?”

“Need to integrate... 😂😂😂😂 Still the leftists think there is a chance???”

⁴ Enrico Mentana is the host of the TG (news) on the television channel La7. In a column for a newspaper, he wrote that Pillon was the “only one laughing” because of the rejection of the DDL Zan.

Appendix 2 – Items by de-radicalizing agents (screenshots)

 Arcigay ✓
 October 27, 2021 · 🌐

+++ Omotransfobia, il Senato affossa il ddl Zan. Arcigay: "Classe politica omofoba" +++
 🙄🙄🙄

🗳️ I numeri della votazione con cui il Senato ha affossato questa mattina il testo Zan contro l'omotransfobia sono inesorabili: la nostra classe politica è in larga maggioranza omofoba

🗳️ Il margine con cui la maggioranza del Senato si è espressa, va ben oltre i confini delle destre, dei finti liberali di Forza Italia o dei cinici arrampicatori di Italia Viva. Ci sono responsabilità anche all'interno delle forze politiche in cui militano i parlamentari primi firmatari del testo. Insomma: c'è una responsabilità diffusa della politica, che ne esce fotografata in maniera implacabile.

🗳️ Questo Parlamento non è stato all'altezza delle sfide di questo tempo, l'argine all'omotransfobia continuerà a porlo il Paese, le reti informali, le associazioni, tutte le persone di buona volontà. Non lo Stato, che ancora una volta si gira dall'altra parte.

🙄 Ringraziamo coloro i quali si sono battuti, a tutti gli altri consegniamo la nostra vergogna.

🔍 Qui il comunicato stampa completo ----> <https://bit.ly/3jGRCW1>

Seduta: 0371 Data: 27/10/2021 Votazione: 1

Tipo: **SEGRETA** Fase: **ESPOSIZIONE**

Oggetto:

Risultati

Fonte	Presenti	Votanti	Favorevoli	Contrari	Astenuti
Emiciclo					
Tribune					
TOTALI AULA	288	287	154	131	2

IL SENATO APPROVA

Seguito dell...

👍🙄🙄 179 44 Comments 102 Shares

Arcigay – Facebook

Translation: Homotransphobia, Senate scuttles Zan bill. Arcigay: "Homophobic political class" +++

🙄 The numbers of the vote by which the Senate scuttled the Zan text against homotransfobia this morning are inexorable: our political class is overwhelmingly homophobic

🙄 The margin by which the Senate majority voted goes far beyond the borders of the right-wingers, the fake liberals of Forza Italia or the cynical climbers of Italia Viva. There is responsibility even within the political forces in which the parliamentarians who first signed the text are militating. In short: there is a widespread responsibility of politics, which comes out unrelentingly photographed.

🙄 This Parliament has not been up to the challenges of this time, the levee to homotransfobia will continue to be laid by the country, informal networks, associations, all people of good will. Not the state, which once again turns away.

🙄 We thank those who fought, to all others we hand over our shame

Comments:

“GUYS I'M LOOKING EVERYWHERE, because I honestly can't do it myself, organizations already in place to go to #roma , one thing done right.. without stooping to the bottom like these assholes want.”

“If we fight for the rights of all, we must become aware that we have MORAL DUTIES such as putting our faces out there, going to the streets UNITED and making our voices heard. Raise the fucking voice that one is always afraid to raise.”

Non una di meno – Instagram

Translation:

“ ✨ November 27, let's become a tidal wave again!

After 2 years of pandemic, it's not going "alright..."

The emergency and the health crisis have descended on us

🔵 Since the beginning of the year, there have been more than 90 femicides in Italy, 3 transicides.

🔵 The three-year institutional anti-violence plan expired in 2020 and is still not renewed.

🔵 The freedom income for women escaping violence sums up a hypocritical policy: 400 euros a month for 12 months that cannot guarantee autonomy.

🔵 Migrant women and men continue to suffer violence: they die at sea and in detention centers in Libya or on the borders of Eastern Europe

🔵 Cases of discrimination and violence against trans, queer, and LGBTQIAP*+ people continue to increase

...The measuring cup is full! [Italian phrase that means “enough is enough”, author’s note]

🌟 ON NOVEMBER 27 WE WILL BE IN A DEMONSTRATION IN ROME! We will occupy the streets with our anger:

because we reject a recovery that erases the causes and effects of the pandemic on our lives!

because we are the high and fierce cry of those who no longer have a voice!

because we want ourselves to be alive and free!”⁵

⁵ Post and comments translated by the author.

Odiare ti costa – Facebook

Odiare ti costa

January 22, 2020 · 🌐

LEI SPACCIA?

Abbiamo ricevuto in queste ore una valanga di segnalazioni del video in cui il senatore Matteo Salvini suona al citofono di una casa nella periferia di Bologna, chiedendo a un cittadino tunisino se fosse uno spacciatore, e diffondendo dati sensibili su di lui.

La pubblicazione di dati personali online è una forma di diffusione che deve rispettare una serie di requisiti per essere legittima. La diffusione di nomi, cognomi e indirizzo di residenza di persone fisiche per essere lecita deve ricevere il consenso degli interessati dietro il rilascio di un'informativa; senza tali requisiti la diffusione viola la normativa in materia di protezione dei dati personali.

Una protezione rafforzata è prevista per i dati personali cosiddetti "sensibili" o "particolari" quali origine razziale, etnica, convinzioni religiose, opinioni politiche eccetera, nonché per i dati personali che rivelino informazioni giudiziarie (quali procedimenti penali e carichi pendenti). Senza il rispetto dei requisiti previsti dagli artt. 9 e 10 questi dati personali non possono essere trattati.

Cosa fare in questi casi? La strada migliore è segnalare l'episodio al Garante per la Privacy per violazione degli artt. 6, 7 e 13 del Reg. UE 2016/679. Solamente il diretto interessato può invece proporre reclamo al Garante.

Purtroppo in questi anni fatti del genere accadono sempre più spesso sul web, per questo è necessario conoscere gli strumenti per tutelarsi.

Ovviamente il problema non riguarda solo la violazione della privacy (che comunque comporta un alto rischio di minacce e intimidazioni per le persone coinvolte), ma è innanzitutto un problema etico. Per questo occorre lavorare per far comprendere a chi abita il web che gesti del genere non sono giustificabili e non dovrebbero mai essere compiuti.

[#odiareticosta](#)

4.4K

709 Comments · 715 Shares

Translation:

ARE YOU A DEALER?

We have received an avalanche of reports in recent hours of the video in which Senator Matteo Salvini rings the intercom of a house on the outskirts of Bologna, asking a Tunisian citizen if he was a drug dealer, and disclosing sensitive data about him.

Publishing personal data online is a form of disclosure that must meet a number of requirements to be legitimate. The disclosure of names, surnames, and residential addresses of individuals to be lawful must receive the consent of the individuals concerned behind the disclosure; without those prerequisites, the disclosure violates data protection law.

Enhanced protection is provided for so-called "sensitive" or "special" personal data such as racial or ethnic origin, religious beliefs, political opinions, etc., as well as personal data revealing judicial information (such as criminal proceedings and pending charges). Without meeting the requirements of Articles 9 and 10 these personal data cannot be processed.

What to do in such cases? The best course is to report the incident to the Privacy Guarantor for violation of Articles 6, 7 and 13 of EU Reg. 2016/679. Only the affected person, on the other hand, can file a complaint with the Guarantor.

Unfortunately, in recent years such incidents happen more and more often on the web, so it is necessary to know the tools to protect yourself.

Of course, the problem is not only about the violation of privacy (which in any case carries a high risk of threats and intimidation for the people involved), but it is first and foremost an ethical problem. This is why we need to work to make those who populate the web understand that such gestures are not justifiable and should never be made.

#hatewillcostyou”⁶

Comments:

“We expect the same stance and lawsuits that you will make alongside Sinisa Mihajlovic.”

“To you who are so self-righteous I would like to ask what you think about all the insults that the Bologna coach has received????? Surely all that nastiness is not coming from the side of those you hate. I haven't heard any of you complaining about that how come?????”

⁶ Post and comments translated by the author.

Appendix 3 – Items representing citizen communication (screenshots)

Fedez - Instagram

Translation:

“Two words about the man of the moment, the somnolent Ostellari. Here is Ostellari, he decided that a bill of parliamentary initiative therefore the highest expression of the people, which has already been approved in the Chamber, such as the Zan ddl can safely be blocked by the desire for protagonism of an individual. That is, himself .”

He then proceeds to attack the Lega for its stance on LGBTQIA+ persons, citing a number of statements made by Lega politicians:

“But then again, Ostellari is part of a political line-up that has distinguished itself over the years for its great fight for equality, I would like to decant some of their aphorisms.

'If I had a gay son, I would burn him in the oven,' Giovanni De Paoli regional councilor Lega Liguria.

'The gays? May they start behaving like all normal people,' Alessandro Rinaldi councilor for Lega Reggio Emilia.

'Gays victims of nature's aberrations,' Luca Lepore and Massimiliano Bastoni Lega municipal councilors.

'Gays are a disaster for reproduction and preservation of the species,' Alberto Zelger councilor for Lega Nord in Verona.

'Gay marriage leads to the extinction of the race,' Stella Khorosheva Lega candidate.

'They give injections to children to make them gay,' Lega candidate Giuliana Livigni."

"Someone like Ostellari said there are other priorities at this pandemic moment than the Zan ddl and so let's see those priorities: the Senate had no time for the Zan ddl because it had to discuss Wine Labeling; the reorganization of Coni ; the bilingualism allowance to Bolzano police officers; and not to be missed, the reinstatement of Formigoni's life annuity. So according to Ostellari probably the right to Formigoni's life annuity is more important than the protection of the rights of everyone and people who are discriminated against daily to the point of violence".

"But speaking of the right to life, the president of the Pro-life association, the ultra-Catholic and anti-abortionist Jacopo Coghe who is a friend of the leghist Pillon in recent months has been the first voice to rise against the Zan ddl. However, the antiabortionist failed to notice that the Vatican has invested more than 20 million euros in a pharmaceutical company that produces the morning-after pill. So dear antiabortionists, dear Pillon unfortunately you wasted too much time looking for the enemy outside, and you did not realize that the enemy was at home. What a bad story."

Lapresa twins – Instagram

Comments:

“You had my curiosity, but now you have my attention.”

“emh. I have no words for what I have seen and read there...! love it!”

Luciano Spinelli – YouTube

Luciano Spinelli – TikTok

Yes, I'm gay 🏳️‍🌈

Kosovo

Annex A

Media objects related to actors of radicalization

Media Object 1: Audience Reaction to Actor

Media Object 2: Audience Reaction(s) to Actor

October 30, 2020 · 🌐

Qytetar te nderuar.Distancohem nga ofendimet e avokatit Tome Gashi ndaj legjendes se Patriotizmit Shqiptar te Kosoves, Zonjes Melihate Termkollit,duke filluar nga shpallja e Deklarates Kushtetuese e deri me tani.Grua kjo e cila me kembengulje mbrojti identitetin tone Kombetar edhe atehere kur ishte e rrethuar me tanke Parlamenti i Kosoves. Nuk duhet lejojuar te ofendoj askush,as Tome Gashi dhe askush tjeter. Mendoj qe per kete ofendim denigrues duhet te merret prokurori dhe drejtesia.Eshte paturpesi e madhe te ofendosh nje femer ne nje Televizion Publik, siq eshte ai i RTK-se.Derisa Serbia ka zgjedh nje kryeminister te deklaruar per perverzion dhe askush nuk e ofendon, ne lejojme qe nje gru shume te ndershme dhe patriote te ofendojme ne formen me te rende te mundshme.Turp i turpeve.

👍 46 3 Comments

Media Object 3: Actor Facebook post

1h · 🌐

Gjithmonë më ka pëlqyer shumë satira e Faik Konicës.

Në një shkrim të botuar në ' Gazeta Dielli' mes tjerash gjeta këtë përshkrim satirik të Konicës (për një ish zyrtare të lartë të Stambollit) që sonte më bëri të qesh me lot:

"...një fshatarake me një bark si kadë e me këmbë si magje, me një palë duar të trasha e të pjekura, e me një fytyrë të fryrë e të kuqe si piper t'Ohrit".

Audience reactions to Media Object 3

Media objects related to Actors of Deradicalization:

Media Object 1: Actor graffiti on public walls against women's subjugation

Audience Reactions to Media Object 1

Media Object 2: Actor action overthrowing table

March 12, 2021 · 🌐

Çka në të vërtetë përmbysi tavolina?

Aksioni protestues që realizoi QJKA për 8 Mars, hapi diskutimin tepër të nevojshëm mbi punët e shtëpisë. Kemi pranuar qindra komente e mesazhe në adresën tonë si dhe kemi vërejtur mijëra të ngjashme në mediat e tjera.

Është e rëndësishme të theksohet se shumica e komentuesve janë burra dhe se përgjithësisht komentet ishin fyese e denigruese ndaj aktivisteve protestuese dhe organizatës sonë. Në plot raste ka pasur edhe kërcënime për dhunë fizike dhe seksuale. Abuzimet online ndaj grave në sferën publike e veçanërisht atyre të përfshira në debatin feminist janë tepër të përhapura. Kjo përveç që dëshmon faktin se këta burra refuzojnë të pranojnë që ka gra aktiviste të angazhuara për çështje publike, tregojnë edhe kundërshtimin e tyre për tu ballafaquar me tema të tilla si punët e papaguara që shpërfaqin dukshëm shtypjen e grave brenda shtëpisë.

Burrat u trazuan dhe kjo për neve tregon se aksioni ka prekur me të drejtë të gjithë ata të cilët mendojnë mundin dhe përkushtimin e grave në punët e kujdesit dhe të mirëmbajtjes. Burrat për herë të parë folën për shenjtërinë e tavolinës së bukës të cilën refuzojnë ta shtrojnë. Burrat u frikësuan nga e vërteta e cila flet për shfrytëzimin të grave brenda familjes. Por kjo tronditje është mëse e nevojshme për të reflektuar shoqërisht mbi pabarazitë që po rëndojnë mbi kurrizin e grave. Prandaj, as nuk frikësohemi dhe as nuk e ndalim përpjekjen tonë sepse ne e dimë që s'ka ndryshime pa kundërshtime.

March 8, 2021 · 🌐

PËRMBYSE RENDIN!

Gatimi, hekurësja, furnizimi, pastrimi e plot punë tjera të ngjashme, marrin shumicën e kohës së grave gjatë ditës. Duke qenë shpesh të varura ekonomikisht nga burrat e familjes, gratë detyrohen që të shërbejnë ushqim e të lajnë enët dhe rrobat për ta. Krejt kjo punë e madhe që bëjnë gratë shihet si obligim i natyrshëm i tyre për shkak të ndarjeve tradicionale të roleve gjinore.

Masat kufizuese dhe kriza ekonomike e shkaktuar nga pandemia Covid-19, izoluan edhe më shumë gratë brenda shtëpive me përgjegjësitë e padrejta mbi punët e mirëmbajtjes dhe të kujdesit. Të dhënat tregojnë se tani gratë shpenzojnë kohë në këto punë pothuajse ekuivalentin e një pune me orar të plotë.

Gratë që kishin fatin të jenë të punësuar, punonin dyfish. Ndërkohë, shumicës tjetër që ishin të papuna i'u shtuan edhe më tepër obligimet e kujdesit ndaj anëtarëve të tjerë të familjes.

Edhe para pandemisë, gratë kanë kaluar mesatarisht tre herë më shumë orë sesa burrat në punët e shtëpisë dhe kujdesin për fëmijët.

Punët e shtëpisë janë nënçmuar historikisht dhe në fakt vazhdojnë të mos njihen as si punë. Në këtë mënyrë, gratë lëre më që po shfrytëzohen, por as nuk po ju vlerësohet angazhimi. Në rastet e ndarjes së pasurisë, si te baba ashtu edhe te burri, gratë konsiderohen si të huaja. Atyre nuk ju takon prona, sepse nuk ju njihet puna.

Duhet të njihet kontributi i grave brenda shtëpisë, në atë mënyrë që puna të ndahet barabartë. Duke qenë gjithë ditën në kuzhinë apo duke pastruar të palarat e të tjerëve, gratë nuk po arrijnë të shohin mundësinë e angazhimit në jetën shoqërore.

Punët e papaguara po izolojnë gratë brenda shtëpisë. Kjo duhet të ndryshoj.

Një tavolinë e ushqimit e shtruar me mund e delikatesë, u përmbys sot. Gratë duhet të çlirohen nga shtypja brenda dhe jashtë shtëpisë. Ndërhyrja në kushtet e shtëpisë është ndërhyrje në pabarazitë e shtresëzuara shoqërore. Krahas kësaj, fuqizimi dhe pavarësimi i gruas është i kushtëzuar nga modeli ekonomik i cili duhet të ndërrojë në drejtim të ndryshimeve të thella strukturore. S'pranojmë të na zhvlerësohet puna e as të shfrytëzohemi nga shteti. T'i përmbysim rolet gjinore ashtu siç bëmë sot me tavolinën!

Audience Reaction to Media Object 2

Media Object 3: Actor Artistic performance using Code of Leke Dukagjini as recipe item

January 12, 2018 · 🌐

Receta:
1 enë me miell
Kanuni i Lekë Dukagjinit
1 palë doreza
1 t'hollues
10 unaza për secilin gjisht të duarve
1 shkrepse
Plin për pjekjen e Kanunit derisa masa të shndrrohet në lëngun e zi.
TAG Kryeministrit

YOUTUBE.COM

Tager* Me rastin e 8 marsit Receta: 1 enë me miell Kanuni i Lekë Dukagjinit 1 palë doreza 1 t'h...

Audience Reactions to Media Object 3:

👍❤️ [redacted] and 40 others 2 Comments 6 Shares

👍 Like 💬 Comment ➦ Share

Oldest ▾

[redacted] ❤️
Like Reply 4y

[redacted]
Jashtezakonisht domethenese. 🍌
Like Reply 4y

Media Objects related to Ordinary Users against Deradicalization

Media Object 1: Ordinary user performance referencing Marigona on Instagram

MARIGONA NUK E QËNDIS MË FLAMURIN!

Rreth shqiponjës të përbashkuara,
Me një dëshirë dhe një qëllim,
Të gjithë asaj duke iu betuar,
Të lidhim besën për ndryshim.

Prej lufte asnjëra nuk duhet largohet,
As ajo që nuk e ndjen shtypjen burrë,
Kush është grua nuk dorëzohet,
Po flijohem, po flijohem për të mos vdek kurrë.

Po flijohem, po flijohem për të mos vdek kurrë.

Grushtin lartë do ta mbajm,
Të mbrojm njëra tjetrën në cdo kënd,
Të drejtat tona ne si ndajm,
Këtu patriarkati s'do ketë më vend.

Se Perëndia vet e tha me gojë,
që fuqia saj zotnon përmbi e nën dhe,
Po drejtësia do të rrojë,
për të, për të luftojmë ne!

Oj shqiponjë, shqiponjë, grua e shenjt,
tek ti betohemi këtu.

6,368 views

OCTOBER 2, 2021

Audience Reaction to Media Object 1:

 🙌❤️ next level this message !

43w Reply

 🙌🙌🙌❤️

43w 1 like Reply

 Artiste me plote kuptimin e fjales 🙌🥰

43w Reply

 🙌🙌❤️🙌

43w Reply

 Loqka jeme po te mire e po smart te kam...
te pafsha ne maja te suksesit... le ta kuptojne krejt qe thanja
flokte e gjata e ment e shkurta as nuk ka vlej e as qe
egziston... thjeshte eshte nje thenje e pavlere prej te
pavlereve ❤️

Media Object 2: Ordinary User slam poetry shared on personal Facebook page

- E burri kur te kalterten e sheh,
syte i vizlojne
edhe gruaja gezohet
se mo nuk ja shurdhojne
gezohet edhe qe n'shpi te babes s'e qojne
qe nji kar n'shpi s'un po e bon
n'hoxhallar e n'mjek e maltretojne
ama burrin nuk e kontrollojne
se atij, langun magjik nuk ia kontestojne

- Une qasaj gruas hallin ja kaj'
se ti qe e ki pushtetin, ti lehte qaren ja bon vetit
po asaj qysh ne kry me ja shti
qe s'ka ardhe ne kete toke vec me maru f'mije
qysh me i kallezu
qe ma as sekondin mos me e plak' tu mendu
ty f'mije qysh me t'maru

- More ti,
ku po je i sigurte djali a te plaket burre a gru?!
a nashta ka me dashte djali me burre me u martu?
nji burre ma shume ne shpi me ta pru
qatehere njimend allti kishe gju!

Por jo pse je gezu!
Po, pse krejt projeksionet para syve tu kane rrenu
Se hisen tane,
nuk bon me trashegu nji gru!

and 512 others

15 Comments 72 Shares

May 17, 2021 · 🌐

Traumë patriarkale

- Sa femije jeni ne familje?
- Kater.
- Çika a djem?
- Çika.
- Ishalla ju gezon zoti me një v'lla.

- Sa femije jeni ne familje?
- Kater.
- Çika a djem?
- Çika.
- Ishalla ju gezon zoti me një v'lla.

- Sa femije jeni ne familje?
- Kater.
- Çika a djem?
- Çika.
- Ishalla ju gezon zoti me një v'lla.

- Sa femije jeni ne familje?
- Kater.
- Çika a djem?
- Çika.
- Ishalla ju gezon mami edhe me një v'lla.

- Sa femije jeni ne familje?
- Kater.
- Çika a djem?
- Çika.
- Ishalla ju bon mami edhe me një v'lla.
- Ishalla ju bon mami edhe me një v'lla.
- Ishalla ju bon mami edhe me një v'lla.
- Ishalla ju bon mami edhe me një v'lla.
- Edhe një v'lla.
- Edhe një v'lla.
- Edhe një v'lla.
- V'lla.

Audience Reaction to Actor's Slam poetry

👁️. S'di çka tham tjetër. Komplekse t'pa sherune t'ni çike qe pret duartrokitje prej ni publiku po ashtu me semundje t'njejtit lloj. T'mjerë pasha Zotin, Ai i'u drejtofte se kerkah me toke t'bukes nuk jeni. Tuget me t'i qu.

Like Reply 3y Edited

Semundja nuk eshte veq shtrit.. per qfar vlera asht tu kallxu kjo lop bre. Pffff

Like Reply 3y

Adem !

Like Reply 3y

↳ 3 Replies

Arlind Berisha qeshtu osht kur tmyket truni 😂😂

Like Reply 3y

Qe sta ka rras kerkush nshkoll mesme ska nevoj me bertit me na kallxu krejtve

Like Reply 3y

Nita Hoti goja i lumte a!

Like Reply 3y

↳ 1 Reply

A kur pi permen qito c*ca mkalle qiti pak ti shoh!

Like Reply 3y

↳ 1 Reply

Valla ma femer DRAM se kjo skam pa...

Imagjinone kjo mej mbrojt te drejtat e femrave 😞

(nuk merren gjanat tuj bertit neper rrug e fb veq pse je femer, po tuj u shkollu e tuja kriju terrenin vetes...

Like Reply 3y

Serbia

Appendix: Items for analysis

	Case study	Name	Object
1.1.	Gašić derogatory remarks scandal	Original YouTube Video Capturing Gašić's Derogatory Remarks	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mm tGxFFybZc
1.1.1.		Screenshot of 1.1, 13''	
1.2.	Gašić derogatory remarks scandal	Vučić's Statement on the Reinstallment of Gašić into Government Body	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rs8 bZD5cZ4w
1.2.1.		Screenshot of 1.2, 1'23''	
1.3.	Gašić derogatory remarks scandal	Gligorijević Tweet, Source of #Novinarkenekleče Hashtag	https://twitter.com/Jovanana/status/673627803586273282

1.4.	Gašić derogatory remarks scandal	Krik's #Novinarkenekleče Tweet	https://twitter.com/KRIKrs/status/686621046569611264
1.4.1.		Krik's #Novinarkenekleče Tweet (1.4.) photo	
1.5.	Gašić derogatory remarks scandal	Tweet Report from Novi Sad #Novinarkeneklece Protest	https://twitter.com/nszoranans/status/678998639675592704
1.5.1.		Photo re 1.5	
2.1.	Mika Aleksić Serial Rapist Case	Serbian Actress Eva Ras Comments on Mika Aleksić Case	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rANM_nI2zyA&t=2s&ab_channel=BALKANINFO-Zvani%C4%8Dnikanal
2.1.1.		Screenshot of 2.1	
2.2.	Mika Aleksić Serial	Video Material from TV Show Programme "Mentalno	https://www.novosti.rs/scena/poznati/955821/nije-isto-siluje-legija-siluje-mika-

	Rapist Case	Razgibavanje”, A Morning TV Show	aleksic-skandalozna-izjava-voditelja-razbesnela-srpsku-javnost-video
2.2.1.		Screenshot from the video material 2.2.	
2.3.	Mika Aleksić Serial Rapist Case	News Report on Aleksić's Testimonies to the Court in His Own Defence, on the Website Blic.rs	https://www.blic.rs/vesti/hronika/podmu-kao-pokusaj-ali-uzalud-mika-aleksic-planira-da-svoju-odbranu-iznosi-mesecima-i/b42lyf9
2.3.1		News photo regarding 2.3.,Blic.rs	
2.4.	Mika Aleksić Serial Rapist Case	Facebook Post Published by the Organization Verujem Ti as a Statement of Support for Milena Radulović in the Case against Aleksić	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid0BFa6sSr4W7RHD A7dvJx2EWqwR8KNhD9PDy7WsrSBvSDYHZAJU8XLLCBARsEXHvmJl&id=104208968197790
2.4.1		Visual of the Facebook Post 2.4.	

2.5.	Mika Aleksić Serial Rapist Case	Instagram post published by the organization Ženska solidarnost	https://www.instagram.com/p/CMpiCFAJzUI/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link
2.5.1.		Visual of the Instagram post 2.5.	
2.6.	Mika Aleksić Serial Rapist Case	Report on the Grassroots Action on Solidarity during Mika Aleksić Trial on the Portal Mašina (Masina.Rs)	https://www.masina.rs/aktivistkinje-pruzile-podrsku-zenama-ispred-palate-pravde-pre-pocetka-sudenja-miroslavu-miki-aleksicu/
2.6.1		Photo material re 2.6.	
2.7.1	Mika Aleksić Serial Rapist Case	Tweet of user @ViktorijaQueen. Reaction on 2.2.	https://twitter.com/ViktorijaQueen/status/1351131132516061186?s=20

2.7.2	Mika Aleksić Serial Rapist Case	Tweet of user @ver_tiffany. Reaction on 2.2.	<p>https://twitter.com/ver_tiffany/status/1351293792146567174</p>
3.1.	Jutka Sexual Harassment Case	News Report on the Anonymous Profile Created for the Sole Purpose of Humiliation of Sexual Harassment Victim	<p>https://www.kurir.rs/vesti/drustvo/3214691/pravda-za-jutku-sokantno-botovi-napravili-profil-i-pokrenuli-ofanzivu-na-mariju-lukic-ti-zrtvada-li-se-tako-oblaci-pristojna-zena-majka-dvoje-dece-sramota</p>
3.2.	Jutka Sexual Harassment Case	Amateur footage of the gathering of local men in support of Jutka by a YT user "GorJak GJ"	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VTQwcACS4Sw</p>
3.2.1.		Screenshot re 3.2	

3.3.	Jutka Sexual Harassment Case	Ne Davimo Beograd Tweet Containing a Picture from Support Gathering for Marija Lukić in Brus	https://twitter.com/dizzymissie/status/1132939775474884608
3.3.1.		Photo re 3.3	
3.4.	Jutka Sexual Harassment Case	Tweet by a Recognized Journalist Jelena Radivojević Sharing Visuals Made in Support for Marija Lukić	https://twitter.com/jelradivojevic/status/1222188019530313728
3.4.1.		Screenshot re 3.4.	
3.5.	Jutka Sexual Harassment Case	Tweet Published by Info Centrala, A Local Informational Portal of Jagodina, A City in Central Serbia Reporting on a Women's Gathering in Support of Marija Lukić	https://twitter.com/InfoCentrala/status/1105914085210759168

3.5.1.		Photo re 3.5.	
4.1.	Baka Prase and YouTube Misogyny	YouTube Video Blog on Kika's Channel – "Kraj Drame" (The End Of Drama), Published Oct 16, 2019	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YxE_DsTZ22wQ&ab_channel=Kika
		Screenshot re 4.1.	
4.2.	Baka Prase and YouTube Misogyny	YouTube Video Blog on Baka Prase's Channel – "Narkomanka Me Optužuje Da Sam Pedofil" (A Junkie Accused Me of Being a Pedophile) Published 2020	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-ePVDPKT0vE
4.2.1.		Screenshot re 4.2.	
4.2.2.		Screenshot re 4.2.	

4.3.	Baka Prase and YouTube Misogyny	TikTok Video of User "s.ntntn" Addressing Bogdan Ilić's Toxic Masculinity	https://www.tiktok.com/@s.ntntn/video/6844607851961322758
4.3.1.		Screenshot re 4.3.	
4.4.	Baka Prase and YouTube Misogyny	TikTok Video of User "s.ntntn" Elaborating on Her Previous Statement	https://www.tiktok.com/@s.ntntn/video/6845194826980314373

4.4.1.		Screenshot re 4.4.	
4.5.	Baka Prase and YouTube Misogyny	TikTok Video of User "s.ntntn" Published on 07.02.2020.	https://www.tiktok.com/@klept0mancin/a/video/6844831476647857414
4.5.1		Screenshot re 4.5.	

4.6.	Baka Prase and YouTube Misogyny	TikTok Video of User "elenazflorest" Published on 9.12.2021	https://www.tiktok.com/@elenazflorest/video/7039809459996101894
4.6.1.		Screenshot re 4.6.	

Slovenia

Image 1: An intervention by a Decontramination activist: KILL LESBIANS becomes KNEEL BEFORE LESBIANS.

Image 2. A part of Homygod project web page: TODAY IS A NEW DAY: DON'T WAIT FOR THE SPRING; You should admit it, too! (source: DJND 2013a)

Image 2. Smetnjak visually modifies liberal politician Rober Golob's International Women's Day address: FREEDOM! [the name of the party] Happy holiday to all women and persons who identify as women. (source: Smetnjak Facebook page)

Turkey

Appendices

Figure 4.1. Khutbah of the Presidency of Religious Affairs

Figure 4.2. The Turkish Family Assembly Visuals

Figure 4.3. Men's Organizations Newspaper Clip

Figure 5.1. Gezi Protests Photo by the KAOS GL

Figure 5.2. My Child Documentary

Figure 5.3. Labour Day by Velvele

Figure 6.1. Concert of Gülşen

Figure 6.2. "Karakol" song by Mabel Matiz

Figure 6.3. Rainbow over the anti-gender march

The UK

Appendices

Appendix 1: Paul Joseph Watson's investigative journalism style

Appendix 2: Using “others” to testify against refugees

Appendix 3: Watson's claim that LGBTQ+ Pride has become mainstream

Appendix 4: Watson's misleading mocking of drag shows to insinuate that they are not 'family friendly'

Appendix 5: The J. K. Rowling tweet, photograph, and a better picture of the t-shirt she wore

Appendix 6: Example of the TERF slogan “adult human female”. The person wearing the t-shirt in the photograph is Kellie-Jay Keen-Minshull, a vocal anti-transgender rights activist

Appendix 7: Examples of Rowling's narrative of escalated violence on Twitter

Appendix 8: Screenshots from Hamza's video about attracting women

Appendix 9: Screenshots from Hamza's video about society's perceived failure of men

Appendix 10: Screenshots from Stonewall UK's video about a bisexual Muslim woman

Appendix 11: Screenshots from Stonewall UK's video about transgender parents

Appendix 12: Screenshot of Gendered Intelligence's Instagram post about Bell v Tavistock

Appendix 13: Screenshots of Gendered Intelligence’s Instagram post about how to be a trans ally

Appendix 14: Screenshots of Gendered Intelligence’s posts about toilet provisions

Appendix 15: Examples of The Female Lead’s TikTok posts with celebrities

Appendix 16: Screenshots from The Female Lead’s TikTok posts about the 2022 UEFA European Women’s Football Championship

Appendix 17: Screenshots from The Female Lead’s video about diet culture in the media

Appendix 18: Screenshots from Jammidodger’s video about J. K. Rowling’s tweet

Appendix 19: Screenshots from Jammidodger’s video about online sexism and misogyny

Appendix 20: Screenshots from Claire_training’s TikTok about fatphobia

Appendix 21: Screenshots from Claire_training's video about sexism

Appendix 22: Screenshot from Rachel Oates' video about MGTOW

Appendix 23: Screenshot from Rachel Oates' video about incels

